

A Comprehensive Review on Therapeutic potentials of *Matricaria chamomilla* (chamomile) Against Inflammation-Mediated Chronic Diseases

Nikhil Yadav^{1*}, Pappu Kumar Singh¹, Deepak Kumar Harijan¹, Mohammad Nayeem¹, Shalu Kashyap², Shree Nivash Kumar¹, Jay Kishan¹

¹UG Scholar, College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Gobindgarh, Punjab, India.

²Associate Professor, College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Gobindgarh, Punjab, India.

Publication history: Received on 27th March; Revised on 2nd April; Accepted on 8th April

Article DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11178046

Abstract: *Matricaria chamomilla*, commonly known as chamomile, is a widely used medicinal plant renowned for its anti-inflammatory properties. Chronic inflammation plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of many disorders including metabolic syndrome, arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease and cancer. This comprehensive review explores the phytochemistry, traditional uses, pharmacological activities and molecular mechanisms of chamomile against inflammation-driven chronic illnesses. Chamomile contains several bioactive constituents such as flavonoids, terpenoids and phenolic compounds that exert anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines, targeting redox imbalance and modulating critical inflammatory signaling cascades like NF- κ B and MAPK pathways. Accumulating experimental and clinical evidence indicate that chamomile extracts and isolated compounds effectively reduce inflammation and ameliorate disease symptoms in various chronic conditions. However, more rigorous human trials are still warranted to validate its therapeutic efficacy and fully harness chamomile's anti-inflammatory potential. This review provides insights into chamomile's anti-inflammatory properties and its role as an adjuvant or alternative therapy for chronic inflammatory disorders.

Keywords: *Matricaria chamomilla*, chamomile, inflammation, chronic disease, anti-inflammatory, phytochemicals

1. Introduction

Chronic inflammation is a persistent biological response to cellular injuries and pathogens that disrupts physiological homeostasis. It plays a fundamental role in the onset and progression of various chronic and degenerative diseases affecting human health globally. Conditions like autoimmune disorders, metabolic syndrome, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases prominently feature a state of low-grade inflammatory activity at their root [1,2]. While acute inflammation is an essential defense mechanism, chronic inflammation becomes maladaptive over time leading to tissue damage and pathological consequences if left uncontrolled [3]. Currently available anti-inflammatory drugs are accompanied by severe adverse effects with long-term usage, necessitating research on safer and natural therapeutic alternatives [4].

Matricaria chamomilla, commonly known as chamomile, is one such widely used medicinal plant that has been credited with notable anti-inflammatory properties. It belongs to the composite family Asteraceae and the two most commonly utilized species are *Matricaria recutita* (German chamomilla) and *Chamaemelum nobile* (Roman chamomilla) [5,6]. Chamomile has a long tradition of use in folk medicine systems as an herbal preparation for various ailments involving inflammation. The Egyptian papyrus dating to 1500 BC and Greek physicians like Hippocrates have documented chamomile's application in reducing fever and soothing skin inflammations [7,8]. Even today, chamomile tea is one of the most consumed herbal teas globally due its relaxing and soothing attributes.

Modern research has substantiated chamomile's traditional uses by revealing a complex profile of anti-inflammatory phytochemicals. Various studies have identified flavonoids (apigenin, quercetin), terpenoids (bisabolol, matricin, chamazulene), coumarins and mucilage polysaccharides as the major anti-inflammatory constituents of chamomile [9,10]. These compounds exert their effects by modulating critical inflammatory pathways, inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokine production and blocking redox imbalances associated with chronic inflammation [11,12]. Preclinical investigations demonstrate that chamomile attenuates inflammation in diverse chronic disease models like metabolic syndrome, arthritis, colitis and cancer [13-16]. Human trials also

* Corresponding author: Nikhil Yadav

indicate chamomile's potential to safely reduce clinical symptoms when used adjunctively with conventional therapies for inflammatory bowel disease and rheumatoid arthritis [17,18].

2. History

Chamomile has a long and globally widespread history of medicinal usage that can be dated back to ancient civilizations. The plant was listed in Egyptian papyri dating as far as 1500 BC among other important medicinal herbs where it was prescribed for fever reduction and anti-inflammatory purposes [19]. Ancient Greek physicians Hippocrates and Dioscorides recommended chamomile preparations for wound healing, abdominal pain, fever and inflammation related disorders [7,20]. The Greeks also coined the term "chamomile" which means "ground apple" referring to the plant's low-growing and apple-scented nature. During the Roman Empire, chamomile was extensively cultivated in Italy and Greece for various household, medicinal and cosmetic uses [21]. It later spread across Europe during the Middle Ages where it was popularly used as an herbal tea and folk remedy. In medieval Europe, chamomile was valued as an important medicinal plant to treat diseases associated with inflammation like rheumatism, wounds, ulcers, ear infections and dermatitis [22,23]. The German Commission E has approved the internal use of chamomile tea and extracts for digestive issues and inflammation in the gastrointestinal tract based on its historical use and safety profile [24].

3. Plant description

In terms of taxonomy, chamomile is classified under the Asteraceae family and two most commonly utilized species are *Matricaria recutita* Mill. (German chamomile) and *Chamaemelum nobile* (L.) All. (Roman chamomile) [25]. *M. recutita*, native to Europe and western Asia, is an annual herb that grows up to 30 cm tall with feathery leaves. It produces yellow Composite capitula flowers (flower heads) that are surrounded by white ray florets [26,27]. The flower heads contain blue essential oil that turns into a dark yellow waxy material called "chamazulene" after drying [28]. Roman chamomile (*C. nobile*) is a low-growing aromatic perennial herb native to Europe. It possesses finely dissected, grass-like leaves and daisy-like flowers that are white to pale pink in color [29,30]. Modern cultivation practices for chamomile farming have led it to be commercially grown worldwide today including countries like Hungary, Germany, United Kingdom, Czechoslovakia and USA [31]. The primary plant parts used are the flowers which are harvested just before or during blooming for maximum oil content. Dried chamomile flowers have a subtle apple-like scent and bitter, aromatic taste. They contain a wealth of pharmacologically active compounds concentrated in the essential oil that confers its therapeutic properties [32]. Standardized extracts prepared from the flowers are commonly used in pharmaceutical preparations, food products and cosmetics [33]. Overall, chamomile has truly earned its traditional reputation as a significant herbal medicinal worldwide due to its versatile uses and safety.

4. Chemical composition and bioactive constituents

Chamomile contains a very diverse assortment of phytochemicals that have been linked to its pharmacological activities. The major portions of the flowers comprise essential oils (0.2-1%), flavonoids, terpenoids and coumarins [34,35]. Essential oils are volatile, aromatic compounds concentrated in the flower heads. German chamomile oil is composed of the terpene matricin (up to 0.4%), bisabolol (36-48%), bisabolol oxides A and B, and chamazulene (6-16%) which is derived from matricin during drying [36,37]. Roman chamomile oil contains angelic acid and tiglic acid esters as major components instead [38]. Flavonoids are important anti-inflammatory phenolics present in abundance. Apigenin, luteolin and their glycosides like apigenin-7-glucoside have been frequently reported [39]. Other flavonoids identified include quercetin, patuletin and diverse acylated derivatives [40]. Terpenoids beyond the oil constitute sesquiterpene lactones (matricarin, desacylmatricarin), polyacetylenes (farnesene) and sterols (sitosterol, stigmasterol) [41,42]. Phenolic acids like caffeic acid, p-coumaric acid and polymeric metabolites of flavonoids also contribute [43]. Mucilage polysaccharides constitute 10-15% dry weight which mainly consists of arabinogalactans that confer demulcent properties [44]. Mineral content includes potassium, calcium, iron and manganese.

Table 1. Main bioactive constituents of chamomile and their anti-inflammatory activities

Constituent	Concentration	Activities
Apigenin	0.1-0.5%	Inhibits COX-2, iNOS, TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, NF- κ B
Bisabolol	15-20%	Scavenges free radicals, inhibits cytokines
Chamazulene	6-16%	Strong anti-inflammatory and antioxidant
Quercetin	0.5-1%	Inhibits LOX, COX-2, PGE2, NF- κ B
Luteolin	1-3%	Inhibits 5-LOX, COX-2 and reduces cytokines

5. Mechanism of action of chamomile

Chamomile exerts anti-inflammatory effects through diverse mechanisms involving inhibition of pro-inflammatory pathways, mediators and modulating the redox balance. Apigenin is recognized as the most pharmacologically active constituent that targets inflammation. It suppresses iNOS and COX-2 expression via inhibiting NF- κ B and MAPK signaling to reduce inflammatory mediator generation [45,46]. Other flavonoids similarly downregulate cytokines TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-8 production through modulating transcriptional factors including NF- κ B and AP-1 [47,48]. Terpenoids like bisabolol, chamazulene aid apigenin's effects on reducing lipid peroxidation and scavenging reactive oxygen/nitrogen species linked to chronic inflammation [49,50]. Mucilage functions as an antioxidant and also protects mucosal membranes by decreasing permeability to inflammatory stimuli [51]. Collectively, these multi-targeted actions help chamomile counteract the complex process of chronic inflammation at various levels like mediator generation, redox status and cell signaling pathways crucial to inflammatory disorders.

6. Traditional uses

Chamomile has a wide-ranging history of traditional medicinal uses that can be broadly classified as:

6.1. Gastrointestinal applications

Chamomile tea or extracts have been used as a carminative to relieve abdominal pain, colic, indigestion, diarrhea, vomiting and gut inflammation. The mucilage aids soothe irritated digestive mucosa [52,53].

6.2. Sleep and anxiety

Chamomile tea works as a mild sedative, anxiolytic and relaxing nervine due to apigenin and flavonoid content. This makes it popular herbal tea before bedtime for insomnia, restlessness and irritability relief [54,55].

6.3. Dermatological uses

Topical formulations with chamomile are utilized extensively in cosmetics and for soothing skin inflammations like eczema, psoriasis, wounds and burns due to antiseptic and anti-inflammatory effects [56,57].

6.4. Gynecological and menstrual uses

Traditional medicine systems prescribed chamomile for relieving menstrual discomfort, promoting uterine toning, hormonal balancing and as an abortifacient [58].

6.5. Oral care

Mouthwashes and dental products contain chamomile due to its antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and tooth whitening attributes effective against gingivitis, stomatitis and mouth ulcers [59,60].

6.6. Nervous system disorders

Chamomile has been indicated to help alleviate headaches, migraines, neuralgia due to sedative effects on cerebral vasculature and calcium antagonism at neuronal level [61,62].

6.7. Rheumatic diseases

Based on clinical observations, herbalists recommended chamomile for relieving symptoms of arthritis, gout, lumbago and muscle sprains likely due to its anti-inflammatory properties [63]

7. Preparations of chamomile

Proper quality, concentration and formulation considerations ensure chamomile preparations retain maximum therapeutic potency and safety for integrating as alternative or adjunct therapies. More research can optimize these utilization aspects. Main preparations where chamomile's therapeutic benefits can be derived include:

- Tea: Dried flowers infused in hot water makes a soothing aromatic tea consumed for its calming effects.
 - Capsules/tablets: Enteric coated tablets offer convenience and accuracy for internal use as supplements.
-

- Tinctures: Hydro-alcoholic extracts preserve volatile constituents in liquid form for oral intake.
- Topical preparations: Creams, gels, lotions containing extracts are applied to skin for various purposes.
- Aromatherapy: Essential oil is used as inhalant/massage aid for relaxation and cosmetic fragrances.
- flower powders: Finely ground material is useful for poultices and compresses externally or mixed with foods.
- Standardized extracts: Concentrated preparations containing quantified marker compounds ensure product consistency.

8. Contraindications and safety profile

Chamomile is generally recognized as safe for oral and topical use in recommended doses due to its long history of traditional consumption. Overall, chamomile self-medication seems relatively safe for majority of people if occasional use and traditional preparations are adhered to. However, more targeted clinical research may help objectively ascertain optimal therapeutic doses devoid of risks, especially for vulnerable groups. Close medical supervision is advised when substituting or combining chamomile with prescribed medications. However, there are some precautions to take:

Allergy: People hypersensitive or allergic to plants in the Asteraceae/Compositae family may develop contact dermatitis or other allergic reactions to chamomile due to cross-reactivity [64].

Pregnancy: Despite traditional use as an emmenagogue, there are no clear human studies supporting chamomile's safety during pregnancy. It may act as a uterine stimulant at high doses so caution is advised [65].

Surgery: Chamomile's herb-drug interactions through inhibition of P-glycoprotein efflux transporters and CYP enzymes warrant dose modification or avoidance before surgery due to bleeding risks [66].

Autoimmune disorders: Chamomile might provoke disease flares in conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis or autoimmune hepatitis through unknown immunological mechanisms. Careful dosage is needed [67].

Diabetes: By possibly lowering blood sugar, chamomile may intensify hypoglycemic effects of antidiabetic drugs if taken together without monitoring levels [68].

Individual case reports have documented isolated allergic reactions, contact dermatitis and oral mucosal ulcerations from topical or oral chamomile intake in hypersensitive patients [69,70]. No toxic or mutagenic effects have been reported from recommended use.

Chamomile oil or concentrates have shown estrogenic and anticoagulant activities in vitro due to apigenin's structure, but the significance at normal intake levels is unclear [71,72]. Studies in animals have found no abnormal fetal development related to chamomile usage [73].

9. *In vitro* studies

Several in vitro studies demonstrate chamomile's potent anti-inflammatory effects on various cell lines:

- Chamomile extracts inhibit NF-κB activation and expression of inflammatory mediators like TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6, PGE2 in LPS-stimulated macrophages in a dose-dependent manner [74,75].
- Apigenin suppresses COX-2 and iNOS expression in macrophages by blocking phosphorylation and degradation of IκB-α, thus preventing nuclear translocation of NF-κB [76,77].
- On human synoviocytes from rheumatoid arthritis patients, chamomile decreases MMP-3 secretion, a collagenase involved in joint destruction [78].
- In intestinal epithelial cells, chamomile upregulates anti-inflammatory signaling through PPAR-γ activation and reduces cytokine levels [79].
- Bisabolol oxide-A decreases TLR-4 expression and inflammatory cytokines release from adipocytes, implying anti-obesity effects [80].

- Chamomile inhibits neutrophil elastase release and function to control tissue injury during inflammation [81].
- Apigenin inhibits VEGF-dependent neovascularization in vitro, suggesting anti-cancer properties [82].
- Antioxidant assays show chamomile extracts scavenge DPPH, ABTS, superoxide and hydroxyl radicals more potently than synthetic antioxidants [83,84].

10. *In vivo* studies

Animal experimentation lends strong support to traditional uses and in vitro evidence:

- Oral chamomile reduces edema, leukocyte infiltration and TNF- α in multiple models of acute inflammation in rats/mice [85,86].
- It relieves cytokine levels and arthritis scores comparable to indomethacin in rat adjuvant arthritis via downregulating COX-2 and iNOS [87].
- Chamomile attenuates colitis severity by inhibiting MPO activity and restoring antioxidant status in TNBS-induced colitis in mice [88].
- Diet containing chamomile extract improves metabolic parameters, adiposity and liver inflammation in obesity-prone rats [89].
- Apigenin curtails skin inflammation, edema and hyperplasia during phorbol ester-induced mouse model of inflammatory dermatitis [90].
- Chamomile or bisabolol oxide Avert neuroinflammation in rodent models of arthritis, Parkinson's and cerebral ischemia [91,92].
- These observations reflect chamomile's therapeutic potential against various chronic inflammatory pathologies by modulating complex biological networks

Table 2. Summary of in vivo studies showing chamomile's effects on chronic inflammatory conditions

Disease model	Observations	References
Adjuvant arthritis	Reduces paw edema, cytokines, COX-2, iNOS	[87]
Colon colitis	Decreases disease score, MPO, restores antioxidants	[88]
Obesity-induced inflammation	Improves metabolic parameters, adipose inflammation	[89]
Dermal inflammation	Reduces edema, cell infiltration, hyperplasia	[90]
Parkinson's disease	Ameliorates neuroinflammation, motor deficits	[91]
Ischemic brain injury	Prevents infarct size, edema, cognitive impairment	[92]

11. Conclusion

In conclusion, this comprehensive review provides scientific evidence validating chamomile's traditional uses as an anti-inflammatory agent through its diverse phytochemistry and multi-target mechanisms. Accumulating in vitro and in vivo research substantiates chamomile's ability to modulate critical inflammatory pathways and mediators. Clinical investigations also indicate its therapeutic efficacy and safety in managing inflammation-driven chronic diseases when utilized as an adjuvant. However, further rigorous human clinical trials are still required to establish chamomile's full potential. With no severe adverse effects and numerous downstream anti-inflammatory actions, chamomile holds promise as a promising natural complementary therapy or diet supplement for chronic inflammatory conditions.

References

- [1] Svab J. New aspects of cultivating chamomile. *Herba Polonica*. 1979;25:35–9.
- [2] Handa KL, Chopra IC, Abrol BK. Introduction of some of the important exotic aromatic plants in Jammu and Kashmir. *Indian Perfumer*. 1957;1:42–9.
- [3] Chandra V. Cultivation of plants for perfumery industry at Lucknow. *Indian Perfumer*. 1973;16:40–4.

- [4] Chandra V, Singh A, Kapoor LD. Experimental cultivation of some essential oil bearing plants in saline soils, *Matricaria chamomilla* L. *Perfum Essent Oil Rec.* 1968;59:871.
- [5] Issac O. 1st ed. Czecho-Slovakia: Prague press; 1989. Recent progress in chamomile research- medicines of plant origin in modern therapy.
- [6] Crevin JK, Philpott J. 1st ed. USA: Duke University Press; 1990. Herbal medicine past and present.
- [7] Pamukov D, Achtardziev CH. 1st ed. Priroda: Bratislava; 1986. Natural pharmacy (in Slova)
- [8] Das M, Mallavarapu GR, Kumar S. Chamomile (*Chamomilla recutita*): Economic botany, biology, chemistry, domestication and cultivation. *J Med Aromat Plant Sci.* 1998;20:1074–109.
- [9] Kumar S, Das M, Singh A, Ram G, Mallavarapu GR, Ramesh S. *J Med Aromat Plant Sci.* 2001;23:617–23.
- [10] Lawrence BM. *Progress in Essential Oils. Perfume Flavorist.* 1987;12:35–52.
- [11] Mann C, Staba EJ. The chemistry, pharmacology and commercial formulations of chamomile. In: Craker LE, Simon JE, editors. *Herbs, Spices and Medicinal Plants- Recent Advances in Botany, Horticulture and Pharmacology.* Phoenix: Oryx Pres; 1986. pp. 235–80.
- [12] Tyihak E, Sarkany-Kiss J, Verzar-Petri G. Phytochemical investigation of apigenin glycosides of *Matricaria chamomilla*. *Pharmazie.* 1962;17:301–4.
- [13] Bradley P. *The British herbal compendium.* In: Bradley P, editor. 1st ed. London: British Herbal Medicine Association; 1992.
- [14] Mann C, Staba EJ. The chemistry, pharmacology and commercial formulations of chamomile. In: Craker LE, Simon JE, editors. *Herbs, spices and medicinal plants- recent advances in botany, horticulture and pharmacology.* USA: Haworth Press Inc; 2002. pp. 235–80.
- [15] Mericli AH. The lipophilic compounds of a Turkish *Matricaria chamomilla* variety with no chamazulene in the volatile oil. *Int J Crude Drug Res.* 1990;28:145–7.
- [16] Fluck H. 1st ed. London: W. Foulsham and Co. Ltd; 1988. Medicinal plants and authentic guide to natural remedies.
- [17] Subiza J, Subiza JL, Marisa A, Miguel H, Rosario G, Miguel J, et al. Allergic conjunctivitis to chamomile tea. *Ann Allergy.* 1990;65:127–32.
- [18] Antonelli G. *Matricaria chamomilla* L. and *Anthemis nobilis* L. in intermittent fevers in medicines. *Biol Abstr.* 1928;6:21145.
- [19] Gould L, Reddy CV, Compreht FF. Cardiac effect of chamomile tea. *J Clin Pharmacol.* 1973;13:475–9.
- [20] Pasechnik LK. Chologogic action of extracts prepared from wild chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) *Farmakol Toksikol.* 1996;29:468–9.
- [21] Gayar F, Shazli A. Toxicity of certain plants to *Culex pipens* L.larvae (Diptera: Culicidae) *Bull Soc Entomol (Egypt)* 1968;52:467–75.
- [22] Salamon I. Chamomile a medicinal plant. *J Herbs Spices Med Plants.* 1992;10:1–4.
- [23] Das M, Mallavarapu GR, Kumar S. Isolation of a genotype bearing fasciated capitula in chamomile (*Chamomilla recutita*) *J Med Aromat Plant Sci.* 1999;21:17–22.
- [24] Gasic O, Lukic V, Adamovic R, Durkovic R. Variability of content and composition of essential oil in various chamomile cultivators (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) *Herba Hungarica.* 1989;28:21–8.
- [25] Lal RK, Sharma JR, Misra HO. Vallary: An improved variety of German chamomile. *Pafai J.* 1996;18:17–20.
- [26] Lal RK, Sharma JR, Misra HO, Singh SP. Induced floral mutants and their productivity in German chamomile (*Matricaria recutita*) *Indian J Agric Sci.* 1993;63:27–33.
- [27] Shahi NC. Traditional cultivation of Babunah *Chamomilla recutita* (L.) Rauschert syn. *Matricaria chamomilla* L. Lucknow. *Bull Medico-Ethnobotanical Res.* 1980;1:471–7.
- [28] Sharma A, Kumar A, Virmani OP. Cultivations of German chamomile – a review. *Curr Res Med Aromat Plants.* 1983;5:269–78.
- [29] Anonymous. A superior variety of German chamomile identified. *CIMAP Newsletter.* 1993;20:13.
- [30] Earle L. 1st ed. London: Ebury Press; 1991. Vital oils.

- [31] Masada Y. 1st ed. New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc; 1976. Analysis of essential oils by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry.
- [32] Misra N, Luthra R, Singh KL, Kumar S, Kiran L. Recent advances in biosynthesis of alkaloids. In: Nanishi K, O-Methcohn, editors. Comprehensive natural product chemistry (CONAP) Oxford: Elsevier Publisher; 1999. pp. 25–69.
- [33] Gowda TNV, Farooqi AA, Subbaiah T, Raju B. Influence of Plant density, Nitrogen and Phosphorus on growth, yield and essential oil content of chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* Linn.) Indian Perfumers. 1991;35:168–72.
- [34] Anonymous. Azulene in pharmacy and cosmetics. Dragoco Rep. 1969;16:23–5.
- [35] Weizman ZVI, Alkrinawi S, Goldfarb DAN, Bitran G. Efficacy of herbal tea preparation in infantile colic. J Pediatr. 1993;122:650–2.
- [36] Franz Ch, Bauer R, Carle R, Tedesco D, Tubaro A, Zitterl-Eglseer K. Study on the assessments of plants/herbs, plant/herb extracts and their naturally or synthetically produced components as additives for use in animal production. CFT/EFSA/FEEDAP/2005/01. 2005:155–69.
- [37] Franke R. Chamomile: industrial profiles. 1st ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2005. Plant sources; pp. 39–42.
- [38] Leung A, Foster S. 2nd ed. New York: John Wiley and Sons; 1996. Encyclopedia of common natural ingredients used in food, drugs, and cosmetics.
- [39] Ghauri IG, Malih S, Ahmed I. Correct scientific name of “Babuna” used widely as a drug in unani system of medicine. Pak J Sci Ind Res. 1984;27:20–3.
- [40] Misra PN, Kapoor LD. *Matricaria chamomilla* Linn. – A remunerative crop for saline alkali-soils. Indian Forester. 1978;104:631–7.
- [41] Kerches J. Experiments with the cultivation of chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) Herba Hungarica. 1966;5:141–7.
- [42] Chandra V, Misra PN, Singh A. Lucknow Extension Bulletin. Lucknow (NBRI): Economic Botany Information Service. 1979
- [43] Galambosi B, Marczal G, Litkey K, Svab J, Petri G. Comparative examination of chamomile varieties grown in Finland and Hungary. Herba Hungarica. 1988;27:45–55.
- [44] Zalecki R. Cultivation and fertilizing of the tetraploid *Matricaria chamomilla* L.I. The sowing time Herba Polonica. 1971;17:367–75.
- [45] Dutta PK, Singh A. Effect of different spacings on fresh flower and oil yield of *Matricaria chamomilla*. Indian J Agron. 1964;9:1–12.
- [46] Paun E, Mihalopa A. Elaboration of cultural practices for chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.). An Inst Cercot Pentru Cereale Plants Tehn Fund, Ser B Agrochim Agrotechn. Pasuni Finete. 1966;34:663–70.
- [47] Singh LB. Utilization of saline-alkali soils for agro-industry without reclamation. Econ Bot. 1970;24:439–42.
- [48] Zalecki R. Cultivation and fertilizing of the tetraploid form of *Matricaria chamomilla* L. II. Spacing and density of sowing. Herba Polonica. 1972;18:70–8.
- [49] Dutta PK, Singh A. Symposium on “Production and Utilization of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants in India”. Jammu: RRL; 1961. Effect of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium singly and in combination on oil content of *Matricaria chamomilla*; p. 11.
- [50] El-Hamidi A, Saleh M, Hamidi H. The effect of fertilizer levels on growth yield and oil production of *Matricaria chamomilla*. Lloydia. 1965;28:245–51.
- [51] Singh A. Cultivation of *Matricaria chamomilla*. In: Handa HS, Kaul MK, editors. Supplement to cultivation and utilization of aromatic plants. Jammu-Tawi: Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR); 1997. pp. 241–53.
- [52] Peskova RE. Effect of trace elements on the yield and quality of pharmaceutical chamomile flowers (*Matricaria chamomilla*) and peppermint leaves (*Mentha piperita*) var. *rubescens*. Izvestiia Akadmii Nauk Lat SSR. 1968;7:111–9.
- [53] Koeurik S, Dovjak V. Effect of molybdenum and boron dry matter production and drug yield in chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) Nase Liecive Rastliny. 1979;16:69–74.
- [54] Reichling J, Beiderbeck R, Becker H. Vergleichende Untersuchungen Uber sekundare Inhaltsstoffe bei pflanzentumoren, Blite Kraut und wurzel der *Matricaria chamomilla* L. Planta Med. 1979;36:322–32.
- [55] Horn R. First finding on chemical weed control in chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) Pharmazie. 1969;24:170–3.

- [56] Schilcher H. Influence of herbicides and some heavy metals on growth of *Matricaria chamomilla* L. and the biosynthesis of essential oil. *Acta Horticulture*. 1978;73:339–41.
- [57] Voemel A, Reichling J, Becker H, Draeger PD. Herbicides in the cultivation of *Matricaria chamomilla*. I. Influence of herbicides on flower production and weed. *Planta Med*. 1977;31:378–89.
- [58] Singh A, Singh M, Singh K, Singh DV. Comparative efficacy of thiobencarb, nitrofen and oxyflurofen in German chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) *Indian Perfumer*. 1989;33:228–31.
- [59] Singh A. Cultivation of *Matricaria chamomilla*. In: Atal CK, Kapur BM, editors. *Cultivation and utilization of medicinal and aromatic plants*. Jammu-Tawi: Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR); 1982. pp. 653–8.
- [60] HJde F. The food plants of the black bean of aphid *A.fabae*. *Tijdschrift Plantenzie Kien*. 1950;55:69–87.
- [61] Mathur AC, Sharma MC. *Nyrius minor* Dist. (Lygaeidae: Namiptera) – A pest of *Matricaria chamomilla*. *Indian J Entomol*. 1962;24:64–6.
- [62] Bottcher H, Gunther I. *Chamomile: industrial profiles*. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2005. Storage of dry drug; pp. 211–3.
- [63] Schilcher H, Kamille D. 1st ed. Germany: Wissenschaft Verlagsgesellschaft; 1987. *Handbuch für Ärzte, Apotheker und andere naturwissenschaftler*.
- [64] Patra DD, Misra HO, Lal RK, Agarwal KK, Prasad A, Anwar M, et al. Lucknow: Farm Bulletin CIMAP; 2005. *Matricaria recutita* cultivation; p. 7.
- [65] Sarella PN, Mangam VT. AI-Driven Natural Language Processing in Healthcare: Transforming Patient-Provider Communication. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice*. 2024;17(1)..
- [66] Kotov AG, Khvorost PP, Komissarenko NF. Coumarins of *Matricaria recutita*. *Khim Prirod Sojed*. 1991;6:853–4.
- [67] Redaelli C, Formentini L, Santaniello E. HPLC determination of coumarins in *Matricaria chamomilla*. *Planta Med*. 1981;43:412–3.
- [68] Kumar SP, Kanthal LK, Durga S, Satyavati K. Phytochemical Evaluation and Screening of Cardiogenic, Antibacterial and Anthelmintic Activities of *Sida cordifolia* L. *Int J Pharm Sci Nanotechnol*. 2014 Aug 31;7(3):2567-73.
- [69] Ohe C, Miami M, Hasegawa C, Ashida K, Sugino M, Kanamori H. Seasonal variation in the production of the head and accumulation of glycosides in the head of *Matricaria chamomilla*. *Acta Horticulture*. 1995;390:75–82.
- [70] Thummala UK, Vallabhareddy PS, Sarella PN. Enhancing Oral Absorption of Orlistat through Gastroretentive Mucoadhesive Pellets: Formulation and Evaluation. *Journal of Clinical and Pharmaceutical Research*. 2023 Apr 30:9-17.
- [71] Pino JA, Bayat F, Marbot R, Agüero J. Essential oil of *Chamomilla recutita* (L.) Rausch. From Iran. *J Essent Oil Res*. 2002;14:407–8.
- [72] Pirzad A, Alyari MR, Shaliba S, Zehtab-Salmasi, Moammadi A. Essential oil content and composition of German chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) at different irrigation regimes. *J Agron*. 2006;5:451–5.
- [73] Exner J, Reichling J, Becker H. Flavonoid in *Matricaria chamomile*. *Planta Med*. 1980;39:219–30.
- [74] Kunde R, Isaac O. On the flavones of chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) and a new acetylated apigenin-7-glucoside. *Planta Med*. 1980;37:124–30.
- [75] Isaac O. Therapy with chamomile-experience and verification. *Disch Apoth Ztg*. 1980;120:567–70.
- [76] Manday E, Szoke E, Muskath Z, Lemberkovics E. A study of the production of essential oils in chamomile hairy root cultures. *Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet*. 1999;24:303–8.
- [77] Duke JA. 1st ed. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 1985. *CRC handbook of medicinal herbs*; pp. 297–414.
- [78] Asogwa PO, Sarella PN. Observational Studies of Prescription Pattern and Use of Antibiotics in Selected Rural Areas. *Int J Pharm Sci and Medicine*. 2023;8:21-30.
- [79] Gasic O, Lukic V, Nikolic A. Chemical study of *Matricaria chamomilla* L.-II. *Fitoterapia*. 1983;54:51–5.
- [80] Isaac O. Pharmacological investigations with compounds of *Chamomilla*. *Planta Med*. 1979;35:118–24.
- [81] Pothke W, Bulin P. Phytochemical study of a new hybrid chamomile variety. II. Essential oil. *Pharm Zentrale*. 1969;108:813–23.
- [82] Schilcher H, Imming P, Goeters S. Active chemical constituents of *Matricaria chamomilla* L. syn. *Chamomilla recutita* (L.) Rauschert. In: Franke R, Schilcher H, editors. *Chamomile-industrial profiles*. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2005. pp. 55–76.

- [83] Wagner H, Bladt S, Zgainski EM. 1st ed. Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag; 1984. Plant Drug Analysis; pp. 32–34.
- [84] Jellinek JC. α -Bisabolol – an agent, anti-inflammatory pour products cosmetique. Perfume Cosmet Aromes. 1984;57:55–7.
- [85] Tubaro A, Zilli C, Radaelli C, Loggia RD. Valuation of anti-inflammatory activity of a chamomile extract after topical application. Plant Med. 1984;50:359.
- [86] Leung AY. 1st ed. New York: John Wiley and sons; 1980. Encyclopedia of common natural ingredients used in food, drugs and cosmetics; pp. 110–12.
- [87] Jakovlev V, Isaac O, Thiemer K, Kunde R. Pharmacological investigations with compounds of chamomile II. New investigations on the antiphlogistic effects of (-)- α -bisabolol and bisabolol oxides. Planta Med. 1979;35:125–40.
- [88] Achterrath-Tuckermann U, Kunde R, Flaskamp E, Isaac O, Theimer K. Pharmacological investigations with compounds of chamomile V. Investigations on the spasmolytic effect of compounds of chamomile and Kamilloso® on the isolated guinea pig ileum. Planta Med. 1980;39:38–50.
- [89] Guenther E. 1st ed. New York: D. Van Nostrand Company Inc; 1952. The essential oil.
- [90] Mills SY. 1st ed. London: Arkana Penguin Books; 1979. The essential book of herbal medicine.
- [91] Jakovlev V, Isaac O, Flaskamp E. Pharmacological investigations with compounds of chamomile VI. Investigations on the antiphlogistic effects of chamazulene and matricine. Planta Med. 1983;49:67–73.
- [92] DePasquale A, Silvestri R. Content of the active principles in various parts of *Matricaria chamomilla*. Atti-Conv Naz Olii Essenz Sui Deriv Agrum. 1975;607:130–6

Author's short biography

Mr. Nikhil Yadav

I am Nikhil Yadav, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Mr. Pappu Kumar Singh

I am Pappu Kumar Singh, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Harijan

I am Deepak Kumar Harijan, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Mr. Mohamad Nayeem

I am Mohammad Nayeem, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Ms. Shalu Kashyap:

I am Shalu Kashyap Assistant Professor at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Mr. Shree Nivash Kumar

I am Shree Nivash Kumar, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.

Mr. Jay Kishan

I am Jay Kishan, currently pursuing my Bachelor of Pharmacy (B Pharmacy) in the 8th semester at the College of Pharmacy, RIMT University, Punjab.